

Soil and crop management

Effect of applied and residual phosphorus on yield of wetland rice under acid soil conditions

U. K. Verma, I. P. Sharma, and R. S. Singh,
Agronomy Department, Birsa Agricultural
University, Kanke, Ranchi, India

Wetland rice frequently does not show immediate response to applied phosphorus because of the reduction of ferric phosphate to ferrous phosphate and the hydrolysis of aluminum and iron phosphates on the one hand and the simul-

Effect of applied and residual phosphorus on grain yield of Cauvery rice variety at Kanke, India.

P level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1978	1979	1980	Mean
0	2.3	1.8	0.8	1.6
9	2.5	2.2	1.2	2.0
18	2.6	2.6	1.4	2.2
21	2.6	3.0	1.6	2.4
CD at 5%	ns	0.3	0.2	

taneous fixation of applied phosphorus on the other. However, the phosphate is released in subsequent years.

The response of wetland rice to applied and residual phosphorus was studied under acid soil (pH 5.2) conditions during the 1978, 1979, and 1980 rainy seasons. The soil was sandy clay loam with low fertility (0.6% organic carbon and 10 kg available P/ha). Rice variety Cauvery (a selection from TKM6/TN1) was the test crop. Single superphosphate was applied in 1978.

Applied phosphorus showed no effect on grain yield in 1978 (see table). In subsequent years, the residual effect was marked. ■

Soil test-crop response correlation approach — a prediction equation for economic paddy yields

G. Puri, D. C. Bisen, S. M. Gorantiwar, and
K. S. Patel, JN Agricultural University,
Jabalpur-482 004, India

A multilocal trial was conducted on transplanted paddy rice Ratna as part of an All-India coordinated scheme to investigate soil test-crop response correlations in farmers' fields.

Sixteen treatments out of 32 possible combinations of 4 nitrogen levels (0, 40, 80, 120 kg/ha), 4 levels of phosphorus (0, 30, 60, 90 kg/ha), and 2 levels of potash (0, 30 kg/ha) were randomized at 12 sites. Net plot size was 20 m². Soils were analyzed for physical and chemical characteristics before treatment (Table 1).

The polynomial trend equation was found significant with coefficient of variation 6-38% at only 6 sites. The average control yield was 1.7 t/ha. Yield in treated plots varied from 0.6 to 5.9 t/ha. The average response ratio was 8.6 for N at 120 kg/ha, 6.5 for P₂O₅ at 90 kg/ha, and 7.6 for K₂O at 30 kg/ha. These nutrient levels were statistically significant.

The multiple regression relationship relating yield to added nutrient and

Table 1. Physical and chemical characteristics of soil at Jabalpur, India.

Parameter	Range	Mean
pH	6.4-7.6	6.8
Mechanical analysis		
Sand (%)	50-56	53
Silt (%)	32-38	34
Clay (%)	10-16	12
Organic carbon (%)	0.20-0.65	0.4
Available nitrogen (kg/ha)	224-324	277
Available phosphorus (kg/ha)	2.7-31.9	10.9
Available potassium (kg/ha)	225-851	421

Table 2. Effect of soil test values and added nutrient on yield at Jabalpur, India.

Regression equation ^a	Fertilizer adjustment equation ^b
$Y = 2642 - 192.54 SN^{**} + 120.39 SP^{**} - 2.02^{**} SP^2 + 0.83 SK - 0.0004 SK^2 + 28.18 *FN - 0.05 FN^2 + 18.8 **FP - 0.09 FP^2 - 41.25 FK + 1.7 FK^2 - 0.05 FNSN - 0.039 FNSP - 0.006 FKSK$	$FN = 282 - 0.5 SN - 10 R$ <p>(224-324 kg/ha)</p>
$R^2 = 0.39^{**}$	$F P_2O_5 = 104 - 2.17 SP - 5.56 R$ <p>(2.7-31.9 kg/ha)</p>

^a Significant at 0.01% (**) and 0.05% (*). ^b Figures in parentheses indicate range of applicability.

available fraction of inherent soil nutrient also were calculated (Table 2). The paddy responded significantly to fertilizer N and P. Available N and P also contributed significantly to grain yield.

In the regression equation, the response of a nutrient — linear (+), quadratic (-), and interaction (-) — represents a second degree parabola. This can be mathematically expressed as:

$$Y = a + bf - cf^2 + d.s.f.$$

where Y = grain yield (kg/ha); a = absolute constant independent of soil and fertilizer; b , c , and d = regression coefficients; f = fertilizer dose (kg/ha); and s = soil test value (kg/ha).

By isolating partial derivatives, the formula for optimum fertilizer nutrient for economic yield can be written as:

$$FN = \frac{b - d.s. - R}{2C}$$